

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Glycerol.

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In the course of a preparative work we had to use mercuric chloride and glycerol; our attention was directed to the remarkable ease with which the former became reduced. Blank tests were performed with the exclusion of other organic compounds and it was found that it was glycerol which was responsible for the reduction.

Studies were then instituted to find out the conditions under which the reduction of mercuric chloride was maximum and to ascertain the nature of the products. It was found that the liquid, after the removal of mercurous and mercuric chlorides, contained glyceric aldehyde, and moreover there was copious evolution of a gas which was found to contain formaldehyde and acrolein. The formation of glyceric aldehyde is not a novel feature in the reaction. As early as 1895 Diacon (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1895, *iii*, 13, 862) observed its formation from mercuric chloride and glycerol but so far, no further work appears to have been done on the subject with a view to examine the gaseous products or to study the condition of formation of mercurous chloride.

It appeared from an examination of the reaction products that mercuric chloride acted in three different ways: (i) It first oxidised glycerol to glyceric aldehyde. (ii) It also dehydrated glycerol to acrolein. (iii) The glyceric aldehyde was then spilt up into formaldehyde probably *via* glycollic aldehyde:

Glycerol has been oxidised to glyceric aldehyde by many workers using different reagents, *e.g.*, platinum black (Grimaux, *Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 1276); nitric acid (Fischer and Tafel, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1088); bromine (Fischer and Tafel, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2634); ferrous sulphate and hydrogen peroxide (Fenton and Jackson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 75, 4) and oxygen in the presence of sunlight (Fenton and Jackson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 10). Using lead peroxide Glaser and Morawski (*Monatsh.*, 1890, 10, 578) obtained about 97% yield of formic acid whilst glyceric acid was obtained by Börnstein by the use of mercuric oxide and baryta (*Ber.*, 1886, 86, 3357). The most interesting

results from the point of view of the present work were obtained by Bierry, Henry, and Ranc (*Compt. rend.*, 1911, **152**, 535; 1912, **154**, 1261) who used ultra-violet rays and got formaldehyde along with glyceric aldehyde from glycerol.

Since glycerol has been directly obtained from suger in good yield (D.R.-P. 347604) and starch easily yields glucose, a tentative chart of degradations linking starch and formaldehyde may be prepared :

Different conditions under which mercuric chloride is required, have been carefully studied and it has been found that at 180-182° the reduction is maximum and amounts to 88-90%. The following chart illustrates the results obtained.

Percentage of Conversion.

Glycerol. (c.c.)	Water (c.c.)	HgCl ₂ (gm.).	Temp.	Duration of heating.	Hg ₂ Cl ₂ % conversion.
1.2	15	9.6408	30°	3 hrs.	Nil.
1.2	15	9.0525	60-70°	„	0.13
1.2	15	9.31	100°	„	0.15
1.5	80	12.0711	180°	„	0.60
1.6	80	12.972	100°	„ (under pressure)	0.30
1.6	60	10.003	120-25°	„ „	0.36
5.5	nil	5.6262	100-05°	3 hrs.	0.33
10.5	nil	6.836	120-25°	„	1.80
10.5	nil	5.0045	150-55°	„	46.71
5.5	nil	5.550	180-82°	„	88.00 (A)
5.5 (anhy- drous)	nil	5.1568	150-55°	„	52.90
5.5 „	nil	5.8708	180-82°	„	90.20
6.0 „	nil	6.348	150-55°	„	50.20
6.0 „	nil	5.0549	180-82°	„	89.10

The gases obtained from experiment (A) were absorbed in water and the aqueous solution was analysed.

The simultaneous formation of the two volatile aldehydes in the reaction produced difficulties in their identification and estimation.

The former was done after fixing the unsaturated aldehyde by hydrochloric acid as β -chloropropionic aldehyde, neutralising the mass with sodium carbonate and distilling off the formaldehyde; it responded to all its essential tests including the very delicate test of Remini (formation of a brilliant magenta colour with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, potassium ferrocyanide and hydrochloric acid). The estimation of formaldehyde was done by Romijn's method (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1897, 36, 18) while the total aldehyde was estimated by the bisulphite method; these gave the figures 5.6% and 11.17% for formaldehyde and total aldehyde respectively.

The bisulphite and iodometric methods were tested with Merck's pure formaldehyde solution and comparative experiments showed that the results obtained by the latter one were more uncertain and variable. Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 25, 1036) has reviewed the existing process for the estimation of formaldehyde and recommends the use of the iodometric and cyanide methods for the estimation of formaldehyde whilst the cyanide method is stated by Romijn to give correct figures for formaldehyde in presence of other aldehydes. No work appears to have been done on the estimation of formaldehyde in presence of acrolein; if iodometric method be adopted, the latter produces additional error by its absorption of iodine at the unsaturated bond. The latter method is, according to our experience, defective even in the case of formaldehyde and other saturated lower aldehydes as we observed in each case the formation of iodoform, while the calculation is based on the theory that the aldehyde is quantitatively transformed into the corresponding acid. In the case of acrolein, too, we observed the formation of iodoform so that it will be a second source of error.

The cyanide method and the bisulphite method were then tested and comparative experiments with pure formaldehyde solution showed that the former always gave low results with reference to those obtained by the latter. As no other process could help us in these estimations we adopted it, but evidently the results do not represent the actual picture. Further work in this line and the study of the conditions under which the successive stages of formaldehyde, acrolein and glyceric aldehyde can be individually and exclusively realised are in progress.

Examination of the gaseous products.—A mixture of mercuric chloride (5.55 g.) and glycerol (5.5 c.c.) was heated in an oil-bath at 180°—182°. The gaseous products were passed through 3

wash bottles containing successively Schiff's reagent, silver nitrate and lime-water. Pink colouration developed in the first bottle, which gradually intensified as the reaction proceeded; in the second, the liquid became slightly turbid, while the third one remained unaffected. It was noticed that almost all the gases evolved were absorbed in the first bottle and the rest in the second, while no bubbles appeared in the third. In the subsequent experiment, in order to ensure whether any carbon dioxide was formed or not, the arrangement of absorption-bottles was reversed: the first one contained lime-water. It was found that there was no turbidity which conclusively showed that carbon dioxide was not formed in the reaction and aldehydes were the main products.

In order to examine the absorbed aldehyde, the experiment was repeated by taking 5.4912 gm. of mercuric chloride and 6.930 gm. of glycerol using special type of wash-bottles in which the dipping tubes were connected with small funnels to ensure complete absorption and to prevent back suction of the liquid into the reaction flask. The wash-bottles in this experiment contained simply water. The liquid, after the reaction was complete, was examined for aldehydes after making it up to 250 c.c. The following tests were applied.

For formaldehyde.—(a) Two drops were diluted to 100 c. c. and to this mixture were added 2 c. c. of 1% solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and 1 c.c. of a 5% solution of potassium ferrocyanide and then a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid when a red colouration developed showing exclusively the presence of formaldehyde. This very delicate test was then applied to a pure solution of acrolein prepared especially for the purpose, but no colouration was obtained.

(b) A solution of 1 g. of resorcinol in 3 c.c. of 25% caustic soda was prepared and to it a drop of the stock solution was added; a faint red colouration developed showing also the presence of formaldehyde.

For acrolein.—A concentrated solution of the absorbed gases was cooled by ice; hydrochloric acid gas was then passed through it when oily drops appeared. After 1 hour the oil was separated, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and taken up by ether. The ethereal solution was dehydrated and then evaporated; an oil was obtained having b.p. 125—129° (β -chloropropionic aldehyde boils at 125—130°). This showed the presence of acrolein. The residual

liquor was neutralised by sodium carbonate and was examined; it was found to contain formaldehyde.

Estimation of total aldehydes.—50 C.c. of a standard sodium bisulphite solution were added to 25 c.c. of the stock solution in a flask well corked and kept for 15 minutes; during this time a blank was performed against $N/10$ -iodine.

Found: Total aldehydes in 250 c.c. stock calculated as CH_2O = 0.7735. Hence total aldehydes calculated as CH_2O on the amount of glycerol = 11.17%,

The amount of formaldehyde in 250 c.c. stock solution by the cyanide method was found to be 0.385 gm. Hence formaldehyde = 5.6% on the amount of glycerol taken.

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